

Relationship Marketing And Value Creation To Improve The Customer Satisfaction

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Abstract

The Enterprise shall be considered as a potentially open and contextualized system, which its survival derives from interchanges of external relationships. Nonetheless, the rational dimension is the key point to maintain a high level of competitiveness.

The number of relation and interdependence with third parties is even more increasing, such that it seems to create a dissolution of enterprise's borders and it leads us to redefine which kinds of interconnections are external and internal of itself.

By reaching its interests, the enterprise is constantly reclaimed to manage social dimension relationships, which is a phenomenon that leads not to just economic objectives, but it is based on the value redistribution to the society and to the needs' satisfaction of stakeholders. Social groups, which the enterprise wants to maintain relations with, that are stakeholders, represent strengths able to influence evolutionary dynamics through the exercise's pressures, expectation and opportunities. At the same time, they are influenced by enterprises' activities receiving back from it expectations and resources.

The development of the relational strategy to stakeholders is a fundamental aspect of the enterprise's activity. However, it has been a neglected aspect for long time in many enterprises in our territory, but it is recently meeting a new rush. This is realised through a continuous selection process and valuation of relevant entities relations, from which they create pressures and expectation to satisfy as a priority. In this way, the enterprise is obligated to tune into multiplied and different interests, which can change and evolve, increasing the interdependence between the enterprises' activities and the one made from its social partners. The attention and the personalisation, or "customisation", needed to manage different stakeholders, such different to create a new marketing version of the enterprise, defined as "co-creation value".

In this contest, the quality of communication that the enterprise turns to the external environment becomes a fundamental and essential asset. This, combined with the new ICT technologies, has improved the creation of CRM (customer relationship management), which has induced firms in dealing with a radical change of the concept of marketing, such that it paved the way for the "one-to-one" model.

Keywords: Relationship value, Customer value, Customer Relationship Management, Customer satisfaction

1. Relationship Marketing and value co-creation

There exists a close link between enterprise, environment and its evolutionary dynamics and strategic behaviours of other companies. There have been relevant changes, which have embraced the socio-economics environment, such as the growing pressure of institutions and consumers on enterprises' actions, globalisation and the tendency to standardisation, markets' liberalisation. Thus, these factors have brought the enterprise to deal with a variety of stakeholders, who sometimes strongly opposed their ideas about the homogenisation, on which some multinational were sniffing around. The tendency invasion of specific processes makes the previous assumptions true, such that they have shown an overcrowding reaction, through claims of cultural roots and the desire to establish your own identity. This had created repercussions on enterprises' action, which have needed to revise their marketing strategy, consequently to the growth of competition's heterogeneity and to an even more increased of consumers' background and needs. Thus, it has been assumed to principally highlight the single client and the service quality, made by a personalised "one-to-one" marketing point of view.

The product itself is not anymore the main enterprise' subject, but the client starts to become active and participative, thanks to the offered technologies of the Web 2.0, which contribute to the marketing process and to the product definition. The dismantling of the value chain, in the way that it is traditionally known, redefines a new model of flexibility and specialisation, based on the collaborative relational activations between single internal assets of the enterprise, which is the cause of productions sectors organisation, well known as "reticular". Therefore, if we refer to the enterprise collaboration with external actors, it is possible to highlight an evolutionary participation of firm's supply, which changes proportionally to the consumer and to his lifestyles and it enriches him for its contributions. Some strategies, such as the crowdsourcing, are an example of how the firm's reality shall be considered out of the relational dimension, which links them to the consumers and which the consumers represent a large resource of an intellectual character to exploit.

2 *Relational Marketing and loyalty*

The development of the marketing relational approach must be referred to the so called ‘north school’, which at the end of the ‘80s, it concentrated its studies on services marketing, reaching the definition of ‘relations’ network’. Its scope was the one ‘to identify, establish, maintain, improve and, if necessary, interrupt relations with clients, such to reach the goals of both parties engaged, through a mutual exchange and promises’ fulfilment¹.

This approach has overcome the idea of interchange, known as transaction as the ultimate aim of marketing strategies, adopting a middle-long strategic prospective which has, as real objective, the relations’ development with clients and stakeholders.

The previous assumptions made for the relational marketing can be verified into the business management, which is oriented to marketing, collaboration for value co-creation, active participation of all involved parties and to relation and services value. Nonetheless it is, in brief, an interchange model based on trust and bidirectional activities, which refers to social relationships and information, not just to money and goods only.

Moreover, there is a close connection with the clients’ fulfilment, on which the relational services marketing is even more concentrated across time.

According to Bendapudi e Berry¹, it has been analysed the motivations that push consumers in creating long relationships with provider services ‘enterprises, focusing on the main aspects. In fact, the client desires to establish a long-run relationship with services provider firms and with the dependence grade by which he is going to develop with it. This analysis concludes that the majority of consumers builds up long-term relationships, which consequently are due to a high dependence grade and to a lack of good alternatives, building up untrusting relationships, which promote opportunistic behaviours that break their durability.

In economics terms, the previous valuations are related to an analysis of consumers’ sustained costs, by which it should refer when the relation ends. However, when the relationship births by a common willingness, it generates a loyal climate that today each enterprise tries to reach.

The abovementioned variables describe two of the main relationship’s characteristics and they influence their evolution across time. In fact, the interdependence and the trust stabilize the duress and willingness’ grade, which are at the base of long-terms’ relationships.

The emergence of a cooperative relation requires that both parties must be active in reaching the common result. If one of the two parties feels forced in to the relation itself, it will employ less resources and, thus, it will maintain a merely passive role.

The interdependence is mainly estimated in terms of specific investments. These are negatively evaluated in a forced relationship, since they build up exits’ barriers to end the relationship. Conversely, there are positively related to a voluntary relationship, because they increase the relation’s strength and involvement. For what concerns the involvement, it refers to the consumer’s willingness of being the firsthand promoter of a service/product, which he has already experimented. If the client is highly involved, there will be created approval and sharing of the enterprise’s lifestyle and values’, such that the client voluntary becomes the ambassador of the firm’s brand equity, by which he is related to.

Obviously, Enterprises hope for a high involved relationships’ instauration through the *relationship marketing*. To verify this, according to Hakansson², the priority is to focus the attention to the utilized technology and to the technology integration between both parties. This is a topic that it helps introducing the *Customer relationship management*.

3 *CRM as the application of relationship marketing*

The *customer relationship management*, such as the system of managing the relationships with clients, has increasingly become the main operative translation of relational marketing.

The prospective from which it births is the *customer centric*, which according to the previous assumptions, focuses the enterprises’ processes attention on the client and it wants to deepen his knowledge taking in to

¹ Bottinelli L., *La nascita e lo sviluppo del marketing relazionale*, Quaderno di ricerca n.5, economia.unipv.it.

² Per approfondimenti: Hakansson H., 1987, *Industrial Technological Development: a Network Approach*, Croom Helm, London.

consideration his needs, such that the managerial action would be more efficient to generate customer satisfaction and, consequently, a consumer loyalty.

CRM realises everything by a complex technological platform, both on hardware and software level, in such a way that it can be operative through a firm's *know how*, able to manage these processes.

At the CRM's basis, there is a total prospective change, which refers to the traditional marketing that focuses its attention on selling a specific product and how. Conversely, the only factor that cares the most for enterprises, which adapt the new approach, is the value creation for the consumer, and it goes beyond the sold product itself. According to Levitt³'s increased Product theory, the overall purchase experience generates the client satisfaction, not just the acquired possess of the individual good. Adding to this the undeniable value that the enterprise acquires from the relationship, it gets involved with the counterpart in to a dual creation of value process, in which the firm modifies its products/services on the basis of the clients' offered contributes and according to their grade of satisfaction or disappointment.

Historically, thanks to Peppers e Rogers⁴, at the beginning of the '90s, the first step has been through a so-called "one-to-one" approach, such as a way of doing marketing, which scope is not to satisfy the greatest possible clients' number anymore, but on reaching satisfaction of the major possible number of clients' needs. This means to capitalize the consolidated knowledge resources, across time.

After that, Pine stresses the introduction of the "mass customization⁵", such as a process through which there is the furniture of a realized tailored product done for a client.

A particular interesting aspect, which refers to this process is the evident possibility offered by the enterprise to co-project the product in collaboration and according to the clients' need. In this way, he will be able to reduce the so-called consumer sacrifice, such as the necessary adaptation that a client must take in to consideration when he buys a standardize good, which is not explicitly thought for him.

By the technologic improvement and the firm's investment in software platforms, enterprises have started to collect a great quantity of clients' data, which utilized the CRM term as a synonym of the overall information. However, the authors *Payne and Frow* have been the ones who gave a proper definition about CRM. In fact, they have described it such as: "a business strategy, which through an intelligent utilization of technology and database, comprehensive of useful information of a real clients knowledge, it is direct to understand, anticipate and answer to firm's actual and potential client's needs, with the aim to increase the relationship value, greatly improving enterprise performance⁶".

A CRM strategy is nowadays known as imperative structure composed by macro components: analytics CRM, operational CRM and collaborative CRM, which operate in to macro activity field:

1. To feel and know the clients basis, such as *clusterisation* in basis of their profitability, exploiting internal database's information
2. Interact with the clients personalising answers through communication tools made and adapted for clusters
3. Satisfy and attract the client, such as implementing tactic actions, which improve the client's portfolio value across time, improving results in terms of:
 - *Trading-up*: sell of high quality products with a higher margin
 - *Up-selling*: to increase the quantity of the sold product to the client
 - *Cross-selling*: increase the purchased products variety of the client

During this historical moment, the CRM has to deal with important challenges related to the monitored results. In fact, it also has to take in to account the difference that a great portion of consumers had managed to strategic issues of the enterprise, mainly due to internet spyware mechanisms, that have induced clients to desire more privacy and, thus, to be less available on giving their personal information.

However, by the adoption of the relationship approach from the enterprises, it has drastically modified the business strategy, implementing a holistic facility, based on an overall of firm's principal processes related

³ Pastore A., Vernuccio M. 2008, *Impresa e comunicazione: principi e strumenti per il management*, Apogeo, Trento.

⁴ Pastore A., Vernuccio M., pp. 131.

⁵ Boulding W., Staelin R., 2005, *A customer relationship management roadmap*, Journal of Marketing vol. 69, Duke University, Durham, pp. 155-166.

Si rimanda anche a: Pine B., 1993, *Mass Customization: The new frontier in business competition*. Harvard Business, Boston.

⁶ Boulding W., Staelin R., 2005, *A customer relationship management roadmap*, p. 157.

to CRM. It seems that there is a no-return conclusion, where is not possible to leave apart a competitive position without a relational enterprise-client strategy.

Thus, there exists new broader horizons in to the marketing environment, in which there are still lot of lacks to fill through research and beyond which we can only imagine them.

4. The evaluation model of the customer satisfaction

One the most essential aspects, which enriches the CRM's validity, concerns on the fact that it promotes the improvement of firms results increasing the level of customers' satisfaction and loyalty. There is a strong logic beyond this model, which is called "profit-satisfaction chain". The satisfaction level grows because a deeper clients' knowledge allows the firms to better understand their needs, to suggest better and personalized offers. The growth of customer satisfaction determines an improvement of a resell attitude, which influences its effective purchasing behaviour, with an effect on firms' performance.

Increasing in profit, clients, loyalty, satisfaction

Service value,

Personnel, loyalty, satisfaction, productivity

Figure 1. Satisfaction-profit chain

The client satisfaction represents the totality of technics and strategies finalised in to the maximisation of an experience satisfaction.

Trying to build up in to a quantitative dimension the Customer Satisfaction concept it results to be closely linked to the concept of product/service⁷ quality. One the nowadays most utilised models to measure the clients satisfaction is the Servqual's, in which customer satisfaction can be measured comparing two aspects:

- The expectation with which the client gets closer to the product/service type.
- The product/service evaluation after its consumption/utilisation.

This comparison is usually made through the paradigm of discrepancy. This method consists on subtracting to the perception level of a product/service the expectation level of that product/service. The satisfaction can be understood as a psychological condition, which derives from a gap between the experience estimation and the clients expectation of this experience. Servqual's model identifies, through a factorial analysis, four

⁷ Valdani E., Bussacca B., "La customer satisfaction: un modello di analisi", Egea, Milano 2004.

investigation areas that describe the product/service quality and thus the client satisfaction:

- 1) Tangible factors: they refer to the perceived quality according to the aesthetic and functional product/service's components (for instance physical structure, communication tools, equipment)
- 2) Reliability: it is the enterprise capacity to operate in time and in loyal way. This area present some item which investigate on the formal and substantial correctness of the performance.
- 3) Response capacity: the user judges the enterprise capacity in to building a support system in the operators and users relationship.
- 4) Reassurance capacity: it analyses the personnel ability to reassure clients during the operations, by favouring an ideal environment to welcome their needs. By evaluating the satisfaction level of the client with the Servqual model, it is possible to consider methodologic directions to elaborate some questionnaires. The measure key point, such as the possibility to compare the expectation's prospective, needs these phases:

- To evaluate the client perception in terms of behaviour of the analysed service/object. One example could be: "the facilities of this sport centre are maintained"
- To evaluate the expectation in relation of the object itself. A same item example, which measures an office expectation, could be: "the facilities of this sport centre should be maintained".
- To compare the perception value with the expectation's ones.

If there is a negative value on these variables, the object/service did not satisfied the users' clients. Instead, if this value is positive, it will be higher to expectations, such that it will represent a satisfactory index of consumers. According to the consumer' scale projected by the Servqual model, the attention should be focused in to the realisation of items phase, which represent expectations and perceptions' scales. The items' planning should take into consideration this discrepancy aspect by respecting some indications:

1. Each evaluation element of the product/service will be insert in such a way to match perceptions (for instance, the sport centre xx has a nice and cozy facility) and expectations (for instance, sport centres should have cozy facilities).
2. Items must be built up to equally balance the expectations perception. In particular, it is fundamental to utilise the same qualitative connotations for both perceptions and expectations. For instance, if a cosmetic shop item in to perceptions "the exposition in this sale point is very accurate", it occurs that in to items' expectations we will obtain "it is essential that cosmetic shops sale point's exposition should be accurate".
3. To identify a discrete number of items for each area of the Servqual model (tangible aspects, reliability, response capacity, reassure capacity), in such a way that they will cover each essential component of the product/service.

Conclusions

According to this work, it has been highlighted the relevance that the relational aspect has in to the enterprise environment. The deep knowledge of the ones who are interested to put influence or pressure on enterprises, such as the accurate relationship analysis between actors, are a fundamental path to better catch the essence of the enterprise system complexity, which always remains, however, hard to summarize. This difficulty is the consequence of the fact that the enterprise is built up on resources, from which the human capital is the most interesting and hardest to manage.

This, together with the preparation and clients needs, has been overshadowing, in to the markets, of no e-tech enterprises of customer care, imposing to enterprise investment implementations of firms' tools, which improve the clients' relationships.

The *customer satisfaction analysis* point out a useful exercise to implement the comprehension of the enterprise environment, but it will represent a future fundamental tool in to the enterprises' projects and initiatives, which will be able to identify with a better precision what to communicate and how.

The relationship marketing quality, personalisation and efficacy are seen as essential drivers of the enterprise performance.

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